

An Roinn Oideachais
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Institute of Education

Best-Evidence Literacy Instruction and Intervention for Students with Additional Learning Needs (8-18 Years)

A Review of the Literature

**Prepared by Ellen Reynor, Institute of Education, Dublin City
University, for the Department of Education**

Author Note

Ellen Reynor <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1709-3031>

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Summary

This review evaluated the evidence from a range of meta-analyses from 2011 onwards examining what constitutes effective instruction and intervention in key literacy areas of reading, reading fluency, writing, spelling, vocabulary and intensive intervention for students with learning disabilities. Key findings include the following

- the most effective reading interventions for struggling readers (e.g., 9-18 years) are multicomponent interventions consisting of foundational skills (e.g., phonics, word recognition and fluency, text reading fluency) as well as comprehension strategies and vocabulary development
- The most effective fluency interventions included a range of strategies such as echo reading, repeated reading and choral reading with teacher modelling. One to one teaching with an adult or peer coaching showed higher effect sizes than small groups. Growth in fluency is associated with improved reading comprehension in many studies
- Effective vocabulary teaching strategies included word mapping strategy (WMS) with use of graphic organisers. Peer mediated methods such as peer-tutoring and collaborative strategic reading (CSR) are also effective strategies for vocabulary development
- There is no significant influence of memorisation intervention on spelling outcomes. Phonics instruction was *not* more effective than morphological intervention, even in the early years. Phonics, orthographic and morphological interventions showed significant effects on reading and spelling outcomes which has significant support in the literature. Small group spelling interventions tend to be particularly effective
- Technology applications appear to be more effective with younger students than older students. High-intensity programs combining technology and nontechnology components have a bigger impact on struggling readers than do low-intensity programs and they should be well integrated with classroom instruction and include small groups.
- There is a need for targeted instruction that is data-based at Tier 2 level of intervention with teacher training in the components of small-group interventions

important for the effectiveness of interventions including close monitoring of progress for students with literacy difficulties particularly at Tier 2

- Preservice and in-service teachers require knowledge of designing explicit reading and writing instruction and intervention, how to use literacy assessments to individualise instruction for students and to determine whether they are responding adequately to such intervention

Recommendations

Reading Intervention

- Use of Multicomponent reading interventions that target both lower level (foundational skills) and higher order (vocabulary and comprehension) skills with explicit teaching (Donegan & Wanzek, 2021; Scammacca et al., 2015)
- For older struggling readers, intervention should target reading fluency and comprehension rather than phonics and basic decoding strategies. Use of PALS is effective. (Bemboom and McMaster, 2013; Flynn et al., 2015)
- Vocabulary instruction and interventions can have significant positive effects on reading achievement (Kaldenberg et al., 2015; Kuder, 2017)
- Small group intervention is most effective (Connor et al., 2014; Donegan & Wanzek, 2021; Hall & Burns, 2018)

Writing Intervention

- Writing strategy instruction with use of self-regulated strategy development (SRSD) (Gillespie & Graham, 2014)
- Use of goal setting and graphic organisers to plan writing (Graham et al., 2017)
- Combine reading and writing skills in lessons (Graham et al., 2017)

Comprehension Intervention

- Inference instruction is important (Ellman, 2017)
- Teach summarisation strategies and how to find the main idea (Solis et al., 2021; Stevens et al., 2019)
- Use of mnemonics, graphic organisers and comprehension strategies for general curriculum texts (Ellman, 2017; Solis et al., 2012)
- Text-structure analysis (Hall-Mills & Marante, 2020)

Vocabulary

- Strategies such as mnemonic strategies, word mapping strategy (WMS), keyword strategy should be used. Using graphic organisers and prompts are important. Explicit teaching of these strategies is necessary (Kaldenberg et al., 2015; Kuder, 2017)

Spelling

- Intervention should combine instruction in orthographic and morphological structure of words as well as phonics (Galuchka et al., 2020)
- One to one intervention, focused and suitably paced is most effective (Wanzek et al., 2016)

- Early intervention (Wanzek et al., 2016)
- Traditional individual intervention for severe spelling difficulties should not be substituted for computer-based approaches (Galuschka et al., 2020; Wanzek et al., 2016)

Intensity of Intervention and Professional Development

- In response to the 3-tiered model of support, interventions need to be adjusted accordingly for nonresponders and students with severe literacy difficulties. Use of data-based decision making and evidence is crucial for these students (Filderman et al., 2018; Lemons et al., 2016)
- Professional development is needed for teachers in literacy assessment to support DBI and how to intervene with explicit evidence-based teaching strategies (McMaster et al., 2021; Wanzek et al., 2016)

Overview

This section evaluates the evidence for what constitutes effective instruction and intervention in key areas of literacy for students aged 8-18 years. With this intention, a range of comprehensive and methodologically rigorous meta-analyses by scholars in the field of literacy dating from 2011 have been chosen and evaluated.

Research Question

What are the most effective instructional strategies, methods, and interventions including technology applications, for developing and supporting reading and writing skills for children and adolescents (8-18) year old with learning disabilities?

Key Search Terms

Online search keywords used to identify relevant articles for each sub-question were combinations of the following: “elementary school” OR “middle school” OR “high school” OR adolescents AND “literacy difficulties” OR “reading disabilities” OR “learning disabilities” OR “specific learning disorder” OR “specific learning disabilities” OR dyslex* OR “struggling readers” OR “additional educational needs” AND “instruction” OR “intervention” OR “methods” OR “strategies” AND “reading” OR “writing” OR “reading comprehension” OR “educational technology applications” OR “computer assisted interventions” OR “computer supported reading” OR “curriculum” AND “systematic review” OR “meta-analysis” OR “synthesis” OR “evaluation”. Exclusion criteria: “adult” *OR “college” OR “post-secondary” OR “university” OR “early literacy” OR “kindergarten” OR “early childhood”

Key Data Sources Consulted

This review of systematic reviews included studies between 2011 and 2021. Articles were written in English and published in peer-reviewed journals. Scholarly work fitting the description of the research question were identified from electronic databases including EBSCO, PsychINFO, ERIC Linguistics. The search engine Google Scholar was used to identify articles that might not appear in a systematic review. Handbooks in the field published since 2011 were sourced. Separate searches were made in relevant online journals such as Scientific Studies of Reading, Annals of Dyslexia, Dyslexia, Reading and Writing, Reading Research Quarterly and the Journal of Learning Disabilities. Searches were made in relevant handbooks such as The Handbook of Reading Disability Research and the Handbook of Learning Disabilities.

The reference lists of relevant meta-analyses were also searched for additional meta-analyses.

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Tabulation of Results

Review	Number of studies	Effect size	Learning disability	Age range	Key findings
Flynn, Zheng, & Swanson (2012)	10	Mean ES 0.42	Reading Disabilities (RD)	8-13 yrs	Word identification, decoding, comprehension instruction yielded moderate effect sizes. No significant moderator variables (e.g., age; type of reading skills addressed; focus of intervention). Certain instructional components appear to be important.
Filderman et al. (2018)	15	0.24	RD	K-12	Data-based decision-making most effective in interventions for struggling readers. Monitoring progress with assessment is an important component in decision making regarding individualisation of intervention.
Bemboom & McMaster (2013)	26	Moderate (0.54) across studies	Struggling readers	14-18 yrs	Targeted small group reading interventions with explicit instruction most effective. PALS including passage reading, retelling, main idea questioning, paragraph shrinking proved effective. Peer mediated instruction as effective as teacher directed.
Wanzek et al. (2013)	10	0.10-0.16	Reading difficulties and disabilities	9-18yrs	Extensive interventions (e.g., 75 hours): small but positive effects for word reading, word reading fluency, reading fluency, spelling, reading comprehension. Instructional gp size was not a moderator in this review. Accelerating reading growth may be more challenging in upper grades even when extensive interventions are carried out. Williams
Galuschka et al. (2020)	34		Dyslexia	Mostly upper primary and adolescent studies (5	Efficacy of spelling interventions for the remediation of reading and spelling difficulties. Importance of individual and small groups, morphological and orthographic instruction as effective as phonological. No evidence for

				adults included)	effectiveness of memorisation strategies. Computer-based supportive software positive effects on spelling.
Hall & Burns (2018)	0.49-95		Struggling readers	5-18 yrs	Targeted small-group interventions more effective. Use of trained teachers more effective. Groups of 3 more effective than groups of 10. Length of intervention was not a factor in effectiveness of intervention. Should correctly target students' area of challenge at T2.
Lee & Yoon (2017)	34	0.59	RD	Kindergarten-18yrs	Positive effects of Repeated reading strategy on word reading and connected text reading especially in elementary grades. Repetition is critical.
Kim et al. (2017)	12	0.2	Learning Disabilities (LD)	6-12 yrs	RR increased reading fluency (with or without a model). Benefits from video modelling and word/phrase practice on initial reading.
Hudson et al. (2020)	16		Reading difficulties	7-11yrs	RR with other aspects (modelling, error correction, phrase drill, peer coaching). Small to large effect sizes. Significant effect sizes for 1-1 and small group interventions.
Scammacca et al. (2015)	36	0.21-0.42 (0.45 for RC)	Struggling readers	9-18yrs	Targeted interventions e.g., Vocab, spelling, decoding, reading fluency, comprehension interventions all yielded significant effects.
Donegan and Wanzek (2021)	33		Struggling readers	10-12 yrs	Only multicomponent interventions predicted significant effects for both comprehension and foundational skills outcomes. No systematic evidence that longer or smaller group interventions were associated with larger effects. However, interventions with smaller groups predicted larger comprehension outcomes.
Kuder (2017)	7		LD	12-18 yrs	Vocabulary instruction can lead to improvements in word knowledge. Strategies with largest effect sizes for vocabulary interventions were morphemic analysis, mnemonic instruction, direct instruction, and media instruction (podcasts). Peer mediated instruction also effective

Graham et al. (2020)	87		RD	4-18yrs	Children with RD experience significant writing difficulties compared with chronologically-age matched peers. This was also the case when children with RD were compared to reading age-matched peers.
Gillespie & Graham (2014)	43	0.74	LD	6-18 yrs	Writing interventions had significant effect on the writing quality of writing of students. Most effective methods were strategy instruction (SRSD), goal setting and process writing.
Graham, Collins, Rigby-Wills (2017)	53		LD	6-12yrs	Writing challenges of students with LD (compared to average achieving writers). Lower scores: writing quality, organisation, sentence fluency, vocabulary, spelling, grammar, handwriting, motivation.
Kang, McKenna, Arden, & Ciullo (2015)	10		Learning Disabilities	8-13 yrs	Integrated Reading and Writing studies: students with LD responded to interventions that were multicomponent and included explicit training in cognitive strategies.
Connor et al. (2014)	Report		Reading disabilities or at-risk for RD		Prevention through intensity of instruction. Importance of fluency and comprehension interventions, vocabulary interventions. Collaborative and peer assisted learning important as well as differentiated learning strategies.
McArthur (2013)	31 (19 of these studies 10+ yr olds)	(H/B of Learning Disabilities)	LD, reading difficulties and children at-risk for reading difficulties	6-14 yrs	Computer assisted instruction (computer supported reading with speech feedback on request). Need to combine instruction in phonological skills with CAI to be effective for students with severe decoding difficulties. Combining teacher instruction with CAI is most effective.
Cheung & Slavin. (2013)	20	0.14	Struggling readers	5-10 yrs	Education technology applications have positive but small effect on the reading skills of struggling readers compared to other strategies. Small-group integrated applications tightly integrated with classroom instruction had larger effect sizes (0.32). However, more research required.

Stevens et al. (2019)	23	0.97	Readers identified with RD, reading difficulty, LD or at-risk)	8-18 yrs	Summarising and Main idea interventions supportive of reading comprehension. Use of text structure and paraphrasing with repeated practice effective.
Daniel & Williams (2021)	10		LD and struggling readers	5-18yrs	Self-questioning strategy. Mixed results of effectiveness for comprehension. Type of instruction or grade level did not influence effect of intervention. Length of SQ strategy instruction showed moderate effect size on reading outcomes.
Hall-Mills & Marante (2020)	9	Medium-moderate	adolescents	LD or at-risk of reading failure	Explicit text structure instruction using SCRD has significant effects on expository text comprehension.
Sanders et al. (2019)	10		LD	5-18yrs	Self-regulated strategy development appears to be an effective strategy to improve comprehension for students with disabilities
Solis et al. (2012)	12	Large effect sizes	LD	12-14yrs	Reading comprehension interventions. Strategy instruction in main idea and summarisation most effective
Kaldenberg, Watt, & Therrien al. (2015)	20	0.50 across all studies	LD	11-17yrs	Comprehension instruction for science texts: teaching key vocabulary. Semantic mapping for vocab; direct teaching e.g., precision teaching and mnemonics. Adding a metacognitive component to these-most effective.
Swanson et al. (2014)	16	1.02	LD	9-18yrs	Reading interventions using social studies content. Such interventions have a significant effect on reading achievement. GOs, mnemonics, guided notes, multicomponent comprehension instruction.
Kim, McKenna & Park (2017)	12		LD	9-18yrs	Computer assisted interventions for comprehension. Those that were effective included frequent opportunities for responding and practice, immediate corrective feedback, teacher-directed instruction. More rigorous evidence needed

Narrative Report

This report is based on the key findings from the relevant research syntheses tabulated above. It is organised according to the key themes that arose from the systematic reviews on evidence-based reading and writing instruction and intervention for struggling readers in upper primary and post primary years.

Reading Instruction and Interventions for Struggling Readers

Educators, policy makers and researchers agree that reading instruction is crucial for improving the outcomes of students who are at risk or have reading disabilities. As children progress through school, the demands of reading change and with improving foundational skills such as reading rate and accuracy, vocabulary and reading comprehension become an important focus of instruction. Both domains are important because by upper primary and through post primary school, students are expected to read as a tool to locate, use, and learn information and difficulties in either domain can severely impact reading performance (Connor, Alberto, Compton, & O'Connor, 2014).

Donegan and Wanzek (2021) in their synthesis of 33 reading intervention studies with upper primary school struggling readers examined the effectiveness of intervention area (e.g., a focus on foundational skills, comprehension skills or multicomponent interventions which included both components), and intensity of intervention as potential moderators of effects. Interventions using foundational skills included instruction in phonemic awareness, phonics (advanced strategies for decoding multisyllabic words such as use of syllabication and word parts such as roots and affixes), word recognition, and reading fluency e.g., repeated reading with teacher modelling and feedback, and teacher or peer support throughout the process. Reading comprehension instruction included both explicit vocabulary instruction and comprehension strategy instruction. Explicit vocabulary instruction included direct instruction in word meaning that went beyond teaching definitions to include deeper processing activities including generating examples, nonexamples and creating semantic maps. Comprehension strategy instruction included learning to identify the main idea, learning to summarise texts and self-regulating or monitoring learning strategies while reading. Intensity of intervention included length of intervention and group size as possible moderators of effects. They found positive but small mean effects on foundational and comprehension outcomes for interventions that focused on foundational skills (0.22) or comprehension skills (0.21). However, multicomponent interventions consisting of both

aspects of reading predicted significant effects for comprehension and foundational outcomes. For intensity, interventions implemented in small groups showed significant effects on comprehension. Interestingly, duration of intervention did not moderate student outcomes meaning that longer interventions were not necessarily more effective than shorter ones. The latter finding is supported by other meta-analyses (e.g., Flynn et al., 2012; Scammacca et al., 2015; Wanzek et al., 2013). For example, Wanzek et al. (2013) whose meta-analysis of reading interventions included 9–18-year-olds with reading disabilities (RD) found that extensive interventions (75+ sessions) yielded positive but small effects on a variety of reading outcomes such as word recognition, word reading fluency, text reading fluency, spelling, vocabulary and comprehension. Indeed, it was noted that shorter interventions of up to 40 sessions yielded higher effect sizes for similar reading outcomes. This suggests that shorter, more intense interventions may be more effective than extensive interventions. In addition, no significant differences in student outcomes were noted for grade level and this finding verifies the value of reading interventions for students at post primary level. Although, instructional group size is often noted an important variable (Fuchs et al., 2014), this meta-analysis found that larger group intervention (e.g., 10-15 students) were as effective as smaller group interventions. Most interventions in this meta-analysis were multicomponent ones. Which could be a reflection of the needs of many adolescent students with RD who require instruction in lower-level skills (e.g., decoding, fluency) as well as higher order reading skills such as comprehension (Wanzek et al., 2013).

Flynn et al.'s (2015) meta-analysis for 8-13 yr. old students identified with RD yielded moderate mean effect sizes on measures of word identification ($M = 0.41$), decoding ($M = 0.43$), and comprehension ($M = 0.73$). However, the proportion of variance in reading performance accounted for by phonemic awareness and phonics was small indicating that for older struggling readers, additional instructional areas should be included in interventions such as fluency and comprehension. It should be noted that none of the 10 studies included vocabulary instruction. The studies that showed moderate effect sizes shared a number of instructional components such as skill modelling, strategy cues, teaching of new content, explicit practice, sessions of 45-60 minutes, and small groups.

Scammacca et al.'s (2015) meta-analysis of 36 studies with 9–18-year-old struggling readers, focusing on word and text level skills, vocabulary instruction and comprehension, delivered as single or multicomponent interventions. Interventions showed small but significant mean effects. Comprehension interventions were found to have a significantly greater mean effect

size on reading outcomes than fluency interventions, and vocabulary interventions were found to have a significantly greater mean effect size than fluency, word study, and multicomponent interventions. As noted above, shorter interventions (e.g., 5-15 hours) were significantly more effective than longer interventions (e.g., 26 hours or more). Studies with researchers implementing the intervention had significantly larger mean effect sizes than studies in which teachers implemented the intervention when looking at all outcome measures across all studies ($p < .05$). In this context, the importance of specialist training for teachers to deliver effective interventions was noted.

A focus on the components of effective small group reading interventions for adolescents (14-18 yrs.) was the focus of the meta-analysis by Bemboom and McMaster (2013). They found that targeted intervention with explicit instruction was most effective. Use of Peer assisted learning strategies (PALS) (Fuchs et al., 1999) including partner reading, passage retelling, main idea questioning, and paragraph shrinking was particularly effective. Peer mediated strategies were as effective as teacher directed instruction.

Interventions to improve Reading Fluency

Reading fluency difficulties are a hallmark of reading difficulties (Stevens et al., 2017). A strong correlation has been found between students' reading fluency and their ability to understand what they read (Kuhn, 2011). Reading interventions are often less effective at improving reading fluency than other skills such as decoding (Kuhn, Rasinski, & Young, 2018). Therefore, it is important to understand more about effective reading fluency intervention. In Hudson et al.'s (2020) meta-analysis of oral reading fluency (ORF) interventions, 15 of the 16 studies reported significant gains in ORF, although effect sizes varied from small to large. Most of the studies included an element of repeated reading (RR). However, none of the studies used RR as a stand-alone element. Supplementary features included choral reading, echo reading, neurological impress method (NIM), teacher modelling of fluent reading, error correction, setting a 'words correct per minute' (WCPM) goal, performance of a text, phrase drill, and use of a peer coach. Interventions that provided an adult in a one-to-one setting appeared to be more effective than small groups. However, interventions that included one-to-one peer coaching also produced large effect sizes. The studies that measured prosody gains reported large significant effects using the NAEP's ORF multidimensional fluency scale to measure gains in prosody which is a valid measure of prosodic reading (Rasinski, Rikli, & Johnson, 2009). Kim et al., (2017) in their analysis of 12

fluency studies focused on children aged 6-12 yrs. Seventy-five per cent of studies included RR with or without a model. Both showed positive effects on reading outcomes. Other successful components of these interventions included word and phrase repetition based on the identification of unknown words and key vocabulary in the passages, error correction and use of familiar passage. The use of video modelling of the text (2 studies) before reading practice also produced significant gains in reading outcomes. In several of the studies, growth in reading fluency was associated with improved reading comprehension outcomes. There were further positive effects for RR strategies especially for word and text reading fluency outcomes in the large meta-analysis by Lee and Yoon (2017) who used a broader age-range range (5-18 years). They found that the repetition element was a necessary component of effective interventions. Using RR with listening passage preview modelled by teachers led to the most significant gains in reading.

Writing Instruction and Intervention

Reading is a subskill required throughout the writing process (Hebert et al., 2018), therefore it is important to examine whether struggling readers also exhibit writing difficulties. In a recent meta-analysis of 87 studies, Graham et al. (2020) found that students with reading difficulties scored lower on measures of writing than their same-age peers. Difficulties with spelling, vocabulary, and syntax particularly hindered children with reading difficulties in their review. One possible explanation for this is that children with RD may not read as much as their same-age peers, and children acquire knowledge about how to spell words, word meanings, and grammar by reading text (Graham, Collins, & Rigby-Wills, 2017).

Examining effective instruction strategies for writing, Gillespie & Graham (2014) conducted a meta-analysis for students with learning disabilities (LD). They found that writing strategy instruction had a statistically significant effect on the quality of writing ($ES=1.09$). This involves students learning strategies for planning, revising, editing, and rewriting texts. Of these studies, instruction in self-regulation strategy development (SRSD) had the highest effect sizes. This strategy teaches students the background strategies and self-regulation procedures necessary to use target strategies effectively and the use of criterion-based instruction. Another strategy that produced positive statistically significant effects was goal setting, where students choose a goal for their composition from a set of goals given by the teacher or were given a goal for revising or including genre elements or were given a set of writing prompts by their teacher. Process writing also yielded significant positive effects on

writing quality. This strategy allows time for students to learn to follow the stages involved in writing and what writing entails, as well as addressing the difficulties approaching the writing process. This process goes beyond instruction in the mechanical components of writing such as text generation and spelling and includes writing for authentic purposes and audiences and offers direct instruction in writing skills as they arise (Graham et al., 2017).

In a similar meta-analysis of 10 studies Kang et al. (2015) found that interventions that combined reading and writing showed positive effects on reading and writing outcomes. Supporting Gillespie and Graham's findings, studies that used such strategies as TWA (Think before reading, think *while* reading, think *after* reading) and PLANS (Pick goals, List ways to meet the goals, and make notes, sequence notes) which are delivered using the SRSD strategy were most effective. (SRSD comprises six flexible stages that include (a) developing and activating background knowledge, (b) discussing the strategy, (c) modelling the strategy, (d) memorizing the strategy, (e) supporting students in using the strategy, and (f) promoting independent performance. Teachers can focus on various stages according to student needs (Sanders et al., 2019)). Additionally, use of graphic organizers as a prewriting and planning tool to support reading comprehension and story elements showed positive effects.

Instruction and Intervention in Reading Comprehension

Solis et al. (2012) argue that teaching students with LD instructional practices for reading text and identifying the most critical information has strong context validity. Their meta-analysis of 12 interventions for students with LD aged 12-14 years (middle grades), examined the most effective instructional practices to improve comprehension. Effective summarisation and main idea interventions had several common features of instruction across studies that should be used as means for supporting improved text comprehension for students with LD. These include instructing students to identify the most important characters, their ideas and happenings in a story. Findings indicated several promising strategies to accomplish summarisation such as including a sequential process, self-questioning, and graphic organizers. Use of a summarising statement including the main idea with a self-monitoring card as a support proved effective. Effective support can be provided through self-monitoring tools such as a checklist or a prompt card. Other strategies that were found effective include use of mnemonics. The most consistent finding across this body of studies was the use of explicit instruction including modelling, feedback, and opportunities for practice. This meta-analysis concludes that students of 12 to 14 years with LD benefit from explicit instruction

designed to support better understanding of text. Supporting the above findings and widening the age range of the study participants, Stevens et al. (2019) meta-analysis examining the effectiveness of summarising and main idea interventions reported a significant mean effect of 0.97 for reading comprehension outcomes of struggling readers aged 8-18 years. Group size, grade level and length of intervention did not moderate the treatment effect. Use of text structure and paraphrasing with repeated practice proved effective methodologies.

The ability to infer from texts is not only considered important for reading comprehension theoretically and in models of comprehension (e.g., Kintsch, 1988) but also practically as inferencing has been shown to be a unique predictor of reading comprehension (Cain & Oakhill, 2007). However, research shows that poor readers often fail to make inferences unless prompted to do so (Barth et al., 2015). In Ellman's (2017) meta-analysis of 25 studies examining the impact of inference instruction on the comprehension of skilled and unskilled readers, results showed that inference instruction was effective for increasing skilled and less skilled readers' general comprehension and inference outcomes and was especially effective in improving less skilled readers' literal comprehension. Another effective comprehension strategy for adolescents is meta-analysis of 9 studies. This includes such strategies as recall of key details, identification of target text structure and strategies such as use of graphic organisers to recall details. All but one study reviewed reported medium to large effects on expository reading comprehension outcomes.

Teaching students to generate questions while reading is thought to have strong of scientific efficacy as a comprehension strategy (NRP, 2000). However, in Daniel and Williams (2021) synthesis of 10 studies with students from 5-18 yr. old using the self-questioning (SQ) strategy, there were mixed results. Type of instruction or grade level did not influence effect of intervention. However, length of SQ strategy intervention showed a moderate effect size on reading outcomes.

Social studies content uses informational text from history, geography and politics for example, and is intended to bolster students' knowledge base through content that is engaging and interesting (Gersten & Okolo, 2007). Indeed, the demands of social studies comprehension and learning highlight the need for practices that support and scaffold students, especially students with LD. Swanson and colleagues (2014) reviewed interventions using social studies text to improve the reading comprehension of students with LD. They examined 27 studies in their meta-analysis. The primary finding was that reading

interventions utilising social studies content had a large positive effect on content and reading comprehension outcomes among students with LD. This finding was true across grade levels. However, the effects appear to be great for older studies e.g., 12-17 years). Interventions with large ESs were graphic organizers, mnemonics, and reading comprehension strategies. However, none of the intervention types appeared to be significantly more effective than the others. It may be that intervention type per se is not as important as applying an organized, structured, text-based intervention to assist students with comprehending and learning social studies content. Interestingly, like previous meta-analyses in this review, duration of intervention was not a factor in overall effectiveness of the intervention. Longer interventions e.g., 500 hours, were *not* more effective than shorter ones e.g., 60 minutes. This meta-analysis was unable to confirm whether size of group was a factor, although it has been found in a number of other meta-analyses that one to one and smaller groups are more effective for younger students and students with severe reading disabilities (Hall & Burns, 2018; McMaster et al., 2018).

Vocabulary Instruction and Intervention

Vocabulary interventions have been shown to improve reading achievement including reading comprehension in past reviews of evidence-based interventions for adolescents with LD (Scammacca et al., 2007). Their review of evidence-based reading interventions for students with LD identified five strategies that were found to improve students reading outcomes: word study, reading comprehension strategies, fluency, vocabulary, and multicomponent methods. Of these, vocabulary had the biggest effect size (1.62). Kaldenberg et al. (2015) in their meta-analysis of effective reading instruction for science classes, found that vocabulary instruction produced higher effect sizes on reading comprehension. They concluded that explicit instruction in content vocabulary was crucial for comprehending science texts. Therefore, it is important to identify evidence-based strategies for teaching vocabulary at post primary level for students with learning disabilities especially with the increased emphasis on independent reading for learning at this level (Vadasy & Nelson, 2012). Kuder (2017) conducted an extension of a previous review of the literature on vocabulary instruction for students with LD by Bryant, Goodwin, Bryant and Higgins (2003) which included 7 studies. It should be noted that 6 of the 7 studies were undertaken in mainstream classes and one in a learning support room. Five of the studies used vocabulary from the classroom and curriculum textbooks, one chose their own vocabulary which contained at least one high-frequency Greek or Latin root and a prefix and/or a suffix, and

one study chose selected lists of words to be learned for an assessment. A variety of strategies were found to produce large effect sizes on vocabulary development. Successful methodologies included use of mnemonic strategies. These were based on teaching keywords through structured mnemonic methods as opposed to drill and practice of new vocabulary. Mnemonic methods consisted of use of a rhyme or a picture to help the student remember information about targeted key vocabulary, or use of a three-step sequence which involved: a) recoding the keyword into a similar sounding familiar word, b) the creation of an interactive picture that illustrates the meaning of the word and can include a sentence that puts the word in context, c) prompting the student to state the meaning of the target word, using the keyword, the description, and the picture. It was found that students recall of vocabulary keywords taught was much better during such mnemonic instruction compared to everyday drill and practice of keywords. A further effective vocabulary method was the use of learning strategies such as a word mapping strategy (WMS), where the morphological structure of words was analysed through identification of the word root and students were encouraged to generate other vocabulary words with the same root. This method consisted of four steps: a) breaking words into their morphemes (e.g., prefix, suffix, root), b) attaching meaning to each word part, c) predicting the meaning of the unknown word based on the meaning of the parts, d) Checking the meaning in the dictionary. Graphic organisers were used by the students to prompt them through the strategy. This was a generative method whereby students were encouraged to transfer their word knowledge to similar words. Interestingly, a nongenerative method was used with another group of students in the same study. This involved use of a keyword strategy, visual imagery, and a story strategy linking known words with unknown vocabulary. As with the WMS, students were guided through the steps with graphic organisers. Students with disabilities in both groups made statistically significant gains in tests of word knowledge, but students in the WMS group outperformed their peers in the other group on vocabulary knowledge and morphological analysis (Kuder, 2017).

Peer mediated methods such as peer-tutoring and collaborative strategic reading (CSR) were also effective strategies for vocabulary development (Connor et al., 2014). CSR uses four steps: a) Preview (activating background knowledge and predicting), b) Click and Chunk, (monitor reading and vocabulary) c) Get the Gist (generating the main idea), d) Wrap-up and Review (summarising key ideas after reading) (Shook et al., 2011). Peer tutoring used partner pairing and immediate corrective feedback to teach vocabulary. Both methods showed that students with LD were able to recall all taught vocabulary a week after the interventions. Two

studies in used podcasts in delivering vocabulary instruction to develop vocabulary in social studies for students with LD. Students who used the podcasts which combined explicit instruction of vocabulary and a mnemonic strategy made significant improvements in vocabulary post intervention.

Altogether, findings show that structured mnemonic methods, morphemic analysis with direct instruction, along with multimedia instruction using podcasts can be effective in developing the vocabulary of students with LD.

Spelling Instruction and Intervention

Spelling is important to both reading and writing (Graham & Santangelo, 2014). Misspelled words make text more difficult to read, and spelling difficulties can interfere greatly with the writing process (Berninger, 1999). Spelling difficulties can influence the words chosen in writing (Graham et al., 2002). A meta-analysis by Graham et al. (2011) found that teachers marked written work with spelling errors more severely for quality of ideas than the same written work with no spelling errors. In this context research on effective strategies and practices that support spelling proficiency is crucial. Galuschka et al.'s (2020) meta-analysis of 34 studies on effective spelling interventions for individuals with dyslexia from early primary grades to adolescents included for the most part, students in upper primary and post primary school. Of note is the finding that there was no significant influence of memorisation intervention on spelling outcomes. Memorisation included mentally picturing the letter sequence of the word and imagining the word in the mind's eye. It was found that phonics instruction was *not* more effective than morphological intervention in the early years. Phonics, orthographic and morphological interventions showed significant effects on reading and spelling outcomes. The evidence indicated that phonological, orthographic, and morphological intervention can be applied across a wide age range. In addition, it was found that instruction on the morphemic structure of words may be particularly effective for children at the upper primary and post primary levels. The effect of phonemic awareness on spelling outcomes was evaluated in one study and did not yield any benefits for reading or spelling. The effects of phonic interventions decreased with age, whereas the effect of morphological and orthographic interventions increased with age. In addition, the efficacy of phonic interventions decreased with severity of spelling difficulty. It appears that knowledge of phoneme-grapheme and grapheme-phoneme correspondence are crucial foundational skills that affect the application of orthographic, morphological spelling rules (Castles et al., 2018),

but these simple grapheme phoneme and phoneme grapheme correspondences do not appear sufficient for skilled spelling. Orthographic and morphological interventions demonstrated moderate to high effect sizes across the age ranges in this meta-analysis. Therefore, it can be argued that graphophonetic and orthographic-phonological spelling rules should be provided alongside morphological instruction as soon as children can master the basic phoneme-grapheme mappings (Galuschka et al., 2020). This concurs with Bowers and Bowers (2017) who argue that the spelling of many words in English can be explained by morphological and orthographic rules and these sources should not be ignored in spelling intervention.

Comparing different intervention settings, it was found that one-to-one interventions showed the largest effect size and classroom intervention the smallest, indicating that classroom intervention may not be specific enough for many students with dyslexia. There were moderate effect sizes for group spelling interventions indicating that small group instruction tends to be particularly effective (Wanzek et al., 2016). Although the effect of age or grade-level could not be determined, early intervention appears to be crucial for effective remediation as spelling difficulties can last a lifetime (Maughan et al., 2009).

A large, and significant mean effect of supportive computer software on spelling skills was found in the one study that evaluated the effect of computer software on spelling outcomes highlighting the potential for supportive software as an additional aid for students with dyslexia and spelling difficulties. However, traditional individual intervention for spelling should not be substituted for computer-based approaches (Galuschka et al., 2020). They advise that computer-based approaches may be useful as an interim measure until individualised instruction is available, and such approaches may be suitable for those with mild reading and spelling difficulties. These findings are consistent with other meta-analyses (e.g., Wanzek et al., 2016), that found students with dyslexia and severe spelling difficulties benefit particularly from individualised intervention that is sufficiently targeted and suitably paced.

Technology Applications for Improving Literacy

The potential of technological applications to improve reading achievement for struggling readers has been anticipated for many years (Lever-Duffy & McDonald, 2008). Cheung and Slavin (2013) examined the effectiveness of educational technology applications on the reading outcomes of struggling readers aged five to ten years in their synthesis of 22 studies. They found some evidence that technology applications for struggling readers may be more

effective with younger students than older students (Torgesen et al., 2007). The studies that took place at the junior end of primary grades had an overall effect size of 0.36, compared to those at the upper primary grades produced an effect size near zero (0.07). This provides some evidence that early intervention is essential for struggling readers. It also appears that high-intensity programs had a bigger impact on struggling readers than did low-intensity programs. The effect sizes for low-intensity and high intensity programs were 0.08 and 0.19, respectively. Use of applications with small groups tightly integrated with the reading curriculum had larger effect sizes (0.32). Importantly, the majority of these high-intensity programs combined technology and nontechnology components in their reading interventions e.g., programmes that were well integrated with classroom instruction and took place in small groups. The programmes consisted of computer and noncomputer activities taught consistently for up to 50 minutes daily. Examples of such programmes are Read, Write and Type (RWT) and Lindemood Phoneme Sequence Programme (LIPS). Overall, it was concluded that computer assisted applications had a small impact on reading achievement of struggling readers, with an overall weighted mean effect size for all programmes included of 0.14.

MacArthur (2013), in his comprehensive review of research on technology for the enhancement of literacy included audio and visual recordings as well as computer applications in the definition of 'technology'. It included 31 studies of which the ongoing work of Olsen, Wise and colleagues in this area was highlighted. Their particular studies (1992-2006) found that the use of computers to support reading of connected text by providing speech feedback on request was effective once students are supported to ask for help with unknown words. Importantly, combining such computer-assisted reading with teacher instruction in reading skills substantially improved the effectiveness of the intervention. However, students with the weakest phonological skills needed more instruction in those skills to benefit from computer-supported reading. Similar to Olsen et al.'s findings, MacArthur's meta-analysis revealed that one of the limitations of computer-supported reading programmes is the lack of detection of reading errors by the student, and the fact that students often do not ask for help when they do not know a word. The results of computer-assisted instruction (CAI) studies based on phonological awareness, decoding skills and word reading, of which there were 9, was mixed, showing nonsignificant findings. However, the strongest effects came from the three studies that combined teacher instruction in small groups with CAI. It was concluded that further research on programmes that integrate teacher instruction with CAI is needed (MacArthur, 2013).

Studies that used assistive technology (AT) for reading comprehension produced mixed results. For example, listening while reading had limited impact on comprehension but electronic text that used speech support with other tools such as online dictionaries, enhanced content features (e.g., graphics and questions) had more positive effects on student comprehension. Some studies that integrated teacher instruction with computer-based instruction showed some positive effects on comprehension and vocabulary, although the research was mixed on such programmes.

There has been relatively little research on writing and technology for struggling readers and writers (MacArthur, 2013). Two such studies using speech recognition software for writing were promising, reporting significant effects on quality of writing (MacArthur & Cavalier, 2004; Quinlan, 2004). More rigorous studies describing baseline conditions and the role of the interventionist are needed to determine whether CAI is an evidence-based intervention or not (Kim et al., 2017). In addition, much research is needed on the advantages and potential barriers and demands of new technologies for learners with reading and writing difficulties.

Guidance on Intensity of Intervention and PD for Teachers

The tiered model of support should be accompanied by a Response to Intervention (RtI) approach to supporting students with additional needs. Fuchs et al. (2014) recommend that, to be effective, interventions should be delivered individually or in small groups (2-8 students) (Connor et al., 2014). Furthermore, interventions should be adjusted according to the seven dimensions of Fuchs et al.'s (2018) taxonomy (strength, dosage, alignment, comprehensiveness, attention to transfer, behavioural support, or individualization) in response to specific student needs.

It is important to understand what factors support effective tier 2 (T2) instruction. Hall and Burns (2018) meta-analysis of small group reading interventions found smaller groups (e.g., 3) were more effective than larger groups (e.g., 10), although, similar to Scammacca et al., (2015) and others, duration of intervention was not a factor in intervention effectiveness. Interventions that were targeted to a specific reading skill were more effective than more general reading interventions. This finding supports research on the need for targeted instruction that is data-based at T2 level of intervention (Fuchs et al., 2017; Lemons et al., 2016). Teacher training in the components of small-group interventions contributed to the effectiveness of the interventions (McMaster et al., 2018).

Data-based individualisation (DBI) is a framework for using data to guide ongoing adaptations (academic and behavioural needs) to intensify intervention for students who have demonstrated a persistent lack of response to ongoing learning support in school (National Centre on Intensive Intervention, 2013). Filderman et al.'s (2018) meta-analysis across ages (5-18 yrs.) found that data-based decision making was most effective in provision of intervention for struggling readers compared to business as usual (BAU) reading interventions. Monitoring student progress with informal and formal assessment to support decision making was an important component in these studies. DBI should be used as guidance and this methodology can significantly increase intervention effectiveness (Lemons et al., 2016). McMaster et al (2021) in their meta-analysis of 23 studies of teachers' PD in reading intervention, argue that many teachers are unprepared to deliver intensive small group and individualised intervention needed for students with severe literacy difficulties who do not respond to class-based practices (Fuchs et al., 2014). Preservice and in-service teachers require knowledge of designing explicit reading and writing instruction and intervention, how to use literacy assessments to individualise instruction for students and to determine whether they are responding adequately to such intervention (Wanzek et al., 2016). McMaster et al. propose the use of Desimone's conceptual framework (2009) outlining the constituent parts of effective PD needed for teachers to be able to deliver effective intense intervention. Some of the components include active learning, coherence, collective participation, content focus, and duration to increase teachers' knowledge and skills, and improve the content of their instruction and their approach to pedagogy.

Biographical Note

Dr Ellen Reynor is an Assistant Professor and Programme Chair of the Masters in Specific Learning Difficulties (Dyslexia) in the School of Inclusive and Special Education at the Institute of Education, Dublin City University. Along with her work on the MEdSpLD programme, she lectures on several other programmes including the Graduate Diploma in Inclusive Education, Learning Support, and Special Education, and is co-ordinator of the B.Ed. specialism in UDL: Teaching and Learning for Dyslexia and Autism. Ellen has presented her work at international conferences (British Dyslexia Association and European Dyslexia Association (EDA)). Ellen's doctoral research examined the cognitive and linguistic profiles of children with dyslexia and literacy difficulties. She has published a range of articles in the area of literacy and dyslexia.

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*Tabulated references

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